

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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DEVELOPMENT OF UNIT-BASED DASHBOARDS
FOR COMMUNICATING NURSING QUALITY OF CARE DATA

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Iatrogenic events such as patient falls, pressure injuries, central line infections and the spread of infectious diseases are largely preventable, yet they occur with unfortunate frequency in hospitals and other patient care environments throughout the nation. Nurses, as the predominant caregivers in healthcare facilities, are continually examining their practices, policies and procedures to prevent such events. However, due to the lack of robust systems and methodologies for systematically collecting, analyzing and communicating practice-related data, many attempts to improve care quality are hampered. Healthcare facilities struggle to find effective ways to communicate data to staff nurses providing care so that they can undertake analysis and improve their performance and the overall quality of care they provide.

This project was developed to address the issue of quality of care feedback to staff nurses at the unit level. It involved designing and implementing unit-based dashboards to communicate performance data in a manner that would stimulate unit-based discussions related to care improvement. Discussion of performance data would in turn facilitate the engagement of staff nurses in planning effective care improvement interventions. The dashboards were developed with the involvement of nurse executives, managers and members of key departmental and unit-based committees. The dashboards were piloted over a three-month period on two nursing units (an ICU stepdown unit and a medical rehabilitation unit) at Rancho Los Amigos National Rehabilitation Hospital in Downey,

California. As dashboards were created each month, their positive and negative attributes were identified, and suggested changes were incorporated as subsequent dashboards were produced.

The project was evaluated in several ways. Pre and post-project questionnaires were administered to staff nurses on the two pilot units to assess their perceived level of involvement in receiving and utilizing quality of care data. The two pilot units were visited throughout the project to ascertain the actual physical presence of the dashboards, and minutes of unit-based “collaborative” committees were reviewed to determine if data were being shared and discussed. Additionally, nurse leaders and members of key nursing departmental and unit-based committees were queried as to their perceptions of the effectiveness of the dashboards in data communication.

While, as revealed from analysis of pre and post-project questionnaires, there were no significant changes in staff-nurse perception of their involvement in quality of care activities, nurse executives and nurses on departmental and unit committees conveyed their strong belief that the dashboards could provide an effective tool for data communication. It was their expressed conviction that, as the department continued in its cultural transformation to become more data-focused, the dashboards would play an increasingly important role in providing important feedback that would assist staff nurses in designing and implementing evidence-based interventions to continually improve care quality.

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INTRODUCTION

This project addressed the development of a formal methodology for communicating quality improvement data to staff nurses so that they could engage in designing and implementing programs, systems and services to improve the quality of care they provide. In this beginning section, a general overview of the area of interest for the project is provided. It identifies the problem being addressed, provides a brief background on the significance of the problem and introduces the conceptual framework that was utilized for addressing the issue.

Background

Seventy percent (70%) of the accidents occurring in United States (U.S.) hospitals are attributed to patient falls (Anderson, Postler, & Dam, 2015). An accidental fall can lead to lengthened hospital stays, physical and psychological patient injury, degradation in the patient's wellbeing and quality of life and even death (Anderson et al., 2015; Interdisciplinary Nursing Quality Research Initiative, 2017). But falls represent only one type of iatrogenic event that can lead to these untoward sequelae. Others include such incidents as hospital-acquired pressure injuries, infections caused by indwelling catheters and intravenous lines and simply not providing or missing needed care (Chapman, Rahman, Courtney, & Chalmers, 2017).

Iatrogenic events are largely preventable. To address them, healthcare leaders must create a culture of quality in their organizations where attention to improving care is ongoing, seen as essential and where successful quality improvement is celebrated (Berwick, James, & Coye, 2003). Because nurses represent the largest segment of the healthcare workforce and provide most direct care services, their active involvement in

quality improvement is critical. Where such nursing involvement has occurred, evidence-based protocols have been developed and implemented to screen and monitor patients at risk for untoward events and to trigger the deployment of proven interventions should patients need remedial care. These protocols have dramatically reduced falls, prevented hospital-acquired infections and enhanced the overall quality of care (Interdisciplinary Nursing Quality Research Initiative, 2017).

Undertaking quality-related activities to improve nursing care requires the development of performance metrics and implementation of systems for providing timely and meaningful feedback. Performance feedback allows nurses to target where improvement is needed and then assess the effectiveness of their care. There is a growing body of literature that demonstrates the importance of feedback and how feedback on quality of care directly impacts quality improvement (Giesbers, Schouteten, Poutsma, van der Heijden, & van Achterberg, 2015; van der Veer et al., 2011). Not surprisingly, the timing and manner that feedback is provided can either stimulate quality improvement and the perceived well-being of nurses or detract from it (Giesbers et al., 2015).

Meaningful feedback about the quality of nursing care needs to be related to indicators that specifically address the care for which nurses hold primary responsibility. Such indicators have become known as “Nursing Sensitive Indicators (NSIs)” and include measures such as hospital acquired infections, pressure injuries, restraint use, patient falls, and patient satisfaction with nursing care (Heslop & Lu, 2014). To assist nursing departments in assessing the care they provide, several regional and national data repositories were created. These repositories provide a rich and ever-growing body of data that can be utilized by hospitals and other healthcare agencies to compare their

facilities to others and internally compare the quality of care they provide from one nursing unit to another. When contracting with such repositories, hospital and unit-specific data are uploaded into the national/regional databases and it is then possible to generate comparative, on-demand reports that are filtered, as desired, by specific NSIs, timeframes and/or benchmark facilities.

Rancho Los Amigos National Rehabilitation Hospital (Rancho) is internationally recognized for its research in rehabilitation and is consistently ranked as one of the best rehabilitation hospitals in the United States. It provides care for over 4,000 inpatients and 71,000 outpatients each year (Health Services Los Angeles County, 2017). The Rancho Department of Nursing recently reorganized and established an innovative, decentralized system of councils to maximize staff nurse engagement. A Department-wide Coordinating Council was established with five sub-councils: (1) Management Council, (2) Professional and Educational Council, (3) Evidence-Based Practice Council, (4) Research and Advanced Practice Council and (5) Quality, Safety and Outcomes Council (QSOC). The QSOC has responsibility for dealing with issues relating to care quality. In addition to the governance councils, each nursing unit has a Collaborative Council (Colab). The Colabs are comprised of unit-based staff nurses, nurse leaders/managers and members of the interdisciplinary team. Colabs are charged with addressing administrative, clinical and quality of care issues on their units.

The Rancho Nursing Department has robust programs for identifying patients at risk for falls and/or potentially developing infections, pressure injuries and other conditions that are monitored through NSIs. These programs contain evidence-based protocols for patient assessment, monitoring and deployment of strategies to prevent

hospital-acquired injury or illness. They also contain patient-specific interventions should such illness or injury occur.

A great deal of internal data is generated through these state-of-the-art programs. Additionally, Rancho contracts with several data repositories that contain NSI data as well as a nationally prominent firm that routinely samples patient perceptions of care and patient satisfaction. Managers within the Department of Nursing at Rancho regularly receive and review reports that are either internally developed or are generated from these repositories. However, there has been no system in place for routinely sharing these reports with nursing staff at the unit level and when such feedback is not received, the ability to engage them in meaningful performance improvement activities is hampered.

Problem Statement

Timely and informative communication of quality of care data is not consistently provided to staff nurses at Rancho, thus inhibiting their optimal involvement in monitoring and improving care.

Statement of Purpose

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to improve communication pathways related to feedback on nursing-specific quality of care indicators throughout the Nursing Department at Rancho.

Supporting Framework

The conceptual framework chosen for this project was the Model for Improvement (Figure 1) promulgated by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) for creating rapid-cycle change (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017b). This model has two components. It starts with three key questions to clarify the aim of desired

improvement activities, the metrics that will be utilized to evaluate success of the improvement interventions and the specific change(s) or intervention(s) that will be implemented. Once these questions are answered and a clear identification of a quality improvement intervention has been identified, the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model is used to test the implementation of the intervention in the clinical setting.

The PDSA cycle first involves *planning*. In this stage, a team is formed, specific goals for the project are identified, resources to support the effort are obtained, problem statements are generated, needed actions are formulated, timetables are specified, and evaluative metrics are generated. The *do* stage is where the desired interventions are implemented by the team. The implementation strategies identified in the first stage are executed to achieve desired goals and the specific activities outlined in the timetable are undertaken. Once implementation has occurred, the effects of the intervention are *studied* and evaluated using the metrics identified in the first stage and the overall success of the intervention is determined. Finally, in the *act* component, needed additional actions are identified and undertaken where necessary as indicated through the comprehensive evaluation of the intervention. If, for example, the effort has resulted in achievement of desired goals and has been determined to be successful, the new processes or interventions are formally incorporated into the ongoing activities of the organization. If efforts have not been successful, the cycle is repeated where new approaches are planned, implemented and evaluated (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017c).

To illustrate use of the PDSA model, a recent study was undertaken to reduce unplanned extubations in a children's hospital Neonatal Intensive Care Unit located in

Akron, Ohio. The PDSA cycle was utilized to structure and implement a series of evidence-based interventions to address what was perceived as a high incidence of unplanned extubations. The interventions were planned, implemented, studied and improved, resulting in a statistically significant decrease in unplanned extubations from 3.8 to 2.7 per 100 intubated days (Powell, Gilbert, & Volsko, 2016).

Figure 1. IHI Model for Improvement (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017c).

Model Questions

For the purposes of this DNP project, the first question in the model (“What are you trying to accomplish?”) was answered in the purpose statement provided above. The overall aim was to improve communication strategies for sharing of information about the quality of nursing care provided at Rancho. The second model question (“How will we know that a change is an improvement?”) was answered utilizing the evaluative metrics that were formulated to assess whether there had been an improvement in data sharing. For purposes of the study, the measure of success chosen was that nurses would be able to verbalize that they had received feedback about the quality of care they had

provided. The third key question (“What change can we make that will result in improvement?”) was addressed by engaging nursing staff involved in providing patient care and their leaders in brainstorming meaningful feedback mechanisms that were believed to potentially be effective and efficient. As described in detail later, the feedback mechanism chosen was that of designing and deploying data dashboards that would communicate performance data in a manner helpful for engaging staff in quality improvement activities.

Plan-Do-Study-Act.

The “Plan” for developing, implementing and testing feedback intervention(s) involved:

- Conducting a thorough review of literature,
- Selecting pilot nursing units to be involved in project,
- Choosing a project team that included staff nurses, nurse leaders, and other key stakeholders,
- Selecting “champions” to spearhead implementation activities on pilot units,
- Developing a formal presentation and orientation to the project that included evidence-based studies found in the literature,
- Reviewing existing reports and quality of care feedback data,
- Designing the communication methodologies (dashboards) in collaboration with key committees and stakeholders,
- Designing strategies and timetables for pilot testing the dashboards,
- Developing evaluation metrics for assessing project success, and
- Designing and administering pre-project questionnaires to nurses on the pilot units.

The “Do” component of the model involved implementing and pilot testing the communication interventions designed by the project team. The steps undertaken for this phase included:

- Activating the dashboards on pilot units,
- Undertaking orientation to the project and dashboard implementation plan,
- Monitoring dashboard deployment through review of minutes and direct observation,
- Assessing the actual use of the dashboards on pilot nursing units, and

- Identifying and resolving potential or actual barriers to implementation.

The “Study” activities associated with the project involved the ongoing review of project success by:

- Interviewing staff as to their satisfaction with the dashboards,
- Administering post-implementation questionnaires to pilot unit nurses,
- Reviewing scores on the Nursing Department’s formal staff satisfaction instrument,
- Conducting focus groups with key stakeholders, and
- Developing visual progress reports to communicate project activities to staff.

Finally, the “Act” component of the model involved revision and/or fine-tuning of communication and feedback mechanisms based on the ongoing assessment of meaningfulness and achievement of identified metrics. The steps in this component of the model included:

- Revising dashboards based on evaluation and feedback,
- Developing protocols for institutionalizing the dashboards,
- Reviewing ways that communication efficiency could be further enhanced,
- Designing and revising new metrics to facilitate ongoing evaluation,
- Reporting project successes and opportunities for improvement to all stakeholders, and
- Completing project close-out activities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A review of literature was conducted which focused on the importance of nursing staff involvement in performance and quality improvement activities and the necessity for providing staff with ongoing feedback relative to the quality of care they provide. Following a review of the historical development of performance and quality improvement, the review focused on communications strategies for providing feedback on nursing-specific quality of care indicators, the primary focus of this DNP project. The following electronic databases were searched: CINAHL Cochrane Library, EBSCO, Google Scholar, Institute for Healthcare Improvement, Ovid, ProQuest, PubMed and Wiley Online Library. Search terms included: dashboards, performance dashboards, healthcare quality, nursing-sensitive indicators, performance feedback, quality improvement, quality reporting, report cards, staff communication, visualizations and visual management. Pertinent references cited in other studies were also reviewed as well as relevant gray literature.

Secondary literature searches were conducted utilizing these same electronic databases as well as the Business Source Premier database and the Google search engine for sources related to the development of quality of care and performance improvement strategies in industry, healthcare and nursing. Key search terms for this secondary literature search included: history of quality improvement, healthcare history, healthcare pioneers, Lean management, nursing history, performance improvement, systems improvement, total quality improvement, and Toyota quality management.

Performance and Quality Improvement: The Early Years

The concept of healthcare performance improvement has its underpinnings in work accomplished during the industrial revolution of the 1800s. Through the work of early industrialist pioneers, a “systematic and systemic” focus for performance improvement emerged (Chevalier, 2008, p. 5). During the late 1920s, W. Edwards Deming, a mathematical physicist, became interested in the application of statistical techniques for use in measuring productivity in the manufacturing industry. He was employed by the U.S. Census Bureau where he piloted his techniques, resulting in a productivity increase at the Bureau that was six-times the baseline productivity measurement (British Library, n.d.-b). This led to appointment as an advisor to the Japanese Census following World War II, where Deming had the opportunity to work with his Japanese colleagues in restructuring the country’s flailing manufacturing industry. Through this work, the Japanese manufacturing effort not only recovered from the devastation of war, but it began to flourish.

Total Quality Management and the PDSA Cycle

Deming developed the concept of Total Quality Management (TQM) which was, at the time, a revolutionary approach to management where “all members of an organization participate in improving processes, products, services and the culture in which they work” (American Society for Quality, 2017b, p. 1). Significant within the concept of TQM is the importance of involving front-line managers as well as organizational leaders. As a part of this work, Deming developed the *Plan-Do Check-Act Cycle*, also known as the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle, for continuous performance and quality improvement (British Library, n.d.-b). The model emphasizes the importance

of systematic approaches to improvement and the need for ongoing feedback to those working on improvement projects. Such feedback serves as a catalyst for refining improvement efforts and identifying successful and unsuccessful implementation strategies. The PDSA cycle described in the introduction is widely used today in the business and healthcare industries and serves as one component of the supporting framework for this DNP project.

The Juran Trilogy and the Pareto Principle

As Deming was refining his management approaches associated with quality and performance improvement, Joseph Juran was also working in the same field. He too found his way to Japan where he lectured extensively and introduced the Juran Trilogy, where quality planning, control and improvement are tied together in an interdependent manner (British Library, n.d.-a). One of Juran's most important contributions to the development of the modern approach to performance and quality improvement was his conceptualization of the *Pareto Principle of Unequal Distribution*, a mathematical model demonstrating that a small number of factors are typically associated with a major percentage of the outcomes one sees in a given situation (British Library, n.d.-a). Understanding this phenomenon allows those involved in quality improvement to focus their efforts on those few factors that have the most influence on improvement. Juran's work, like Deming's, emphasized the importance of systematic approaches to quality improvement.

Organizational Waste, Lean Manufacturing and Lean Management

Simultaneous with the efforts described above, following World War II, Taiichi Ohno, an executive of the Toyota Japanese car manufacturing company, identified that

there appeared to be waste (inefficient processes, unnecessary steps, expenditure of resources, etc.) in most manufacturing and service activities. Ohno referred to this using the Japanese word *Muda*. He studied the assembly line created by the Ford Motor Company in America as well as processes utilized in American supermarkets (Epply, n.d.). Ohno believed that productivity and quality could be improved through the elimination of unnecessary waste. His work, focusing on the elimination of waste in production, served as the foundation for development of the concept of Lean Manufacturing (Epply, n.d.). In the 1980s, when Japanese auto manufacturers began to establish their plants in the United States (U.S.), it was quickly learned that their success was largely attributed to their ability to use the principles of waste reduction formulated by Ohno. As companies like Toyota were studied by U.S. systems and industrial engineers, the philosophy of Lean Management emerged and quickly swept the nation. Lean Management concepts have been particularly embraced by the U.S. healthcare industry where today they serve as key tools for redesigning systems to improve the quality, productivity and efficiency of healthcare delivery (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2005). Lean Management, like prior improvement methodologies, emphasizes the need for involvement of those closest to a service or process for redesign to be effective.

Lean Management also needs to be undertaken in a manner which solicits the perspective of those served by the organization, process or system. The opinions of those served should be sought and valued because they are the organization's consumers/customers. A recent study conducted in Sweden emphasized this fact (Poksinska, Fialkowska-Filipek, & Engstrom, 2017). The study compared patient

satisfaction with care delivery in primary care centers actively engaged in Lean Management with a control group of primary care centers not so engaged. Results of the study showed little impact on patient satisfaction just because a center used Lean Management approaches. The study demonstrated that Lean Management is typically utilized to improve healthcare system efficiencies without regard to the patients' perspective of what is of value to them as consumers of healthcare. Hence, improvement efforts might yield systems effectiveness/efficiency but be negatively perceived by those served by the organization. The study concluded that both staff and patient involvement are needed to optimally redesign systems to enhance efficiency as well as patient and staff satisfaction (Poksinska et al., 2017).

Summary of the Early Years

To summarize, the work of Deming, Juran, Ohno and many others laid the early foundation for modern performance and quality improvement systems and processes. Based on the work of these pioneers, performance and quality improvement approaches are now characterized by:

- The need for systemic approaches,
- Involvement of those served by the organization,
- Inclusion of staff at all levels,
- Systematic methods,
- A focus on continuous improvement,
- The development of metrics and goals for performance enhancement,
- Rigor in undertaking improvement activities,
- Transparency, and
- Ongoing feedback to staff and consumers.

Performance and Quality Improvement in Healthcare

The healthcare industry is different in many ways when compared to manufacturing. However, those involved in healthcare quality and performance

improvement have been able to successfully adapt and build upon the work just described to support their healthcare improvement efforts. For example, Health Catalyst, a healthcare quality data warehouse, promotes five of the key principles developed by Deming as making “the biggest difference in healthcare process improvement” (Health Catalyst, 2017, p. 1). Similarly, the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) utilizes Deming’s PDSA model as an important tool in their healthcare consulting and as a key component of their Healthcare Improvement Model (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017c).

Mandate for Involvement of Front-Line Managers

Peter Drucker, one of the most revered management consultants, educators and authors in the U.S., had a strong, early influence on healthcare performance and quality improvement. As far back as 1967, Drucker was espousing the necessity for engaging those on the “front-line” of the organization in any attempt to improve quality (Drucker, 1968; Dunn, 2014, p. 1). Traditionally, quality improvement was seen as a key management function and, while managers at various organizational levels were involved in improvement activities, there was no mandate for including those actually providing the services.

Emergence of Systematic Healthcare Improvement

In the early 1900s, Ernest Amory Codman, a Boston surgeon developed interest in hospital reform and founded an effort that is today referred to as outcomes management (Rodkey & Itani, 2009). Codman was very interested in measuring the performance of surgeons as well as the outcomes of care provided in hospitals. He systematically evaluated the progress of patients from the time of their admission to their discharge and

documented the outcomes of their care on “end result cards” (Rodkey & Itani, 2009). He then analyzed his data and developed comparative reports which demonstrated care delivery approaches that were successful in achieving positive patient outcomes and those that were not. He also developed statistical reports to document medical errors.

In 1913, the American College of Surgeons (ACS) was founded and the organization adopted Codman’s work, developed minimum standards for hospitals and began inspecting hospitals utilizing these standard (American College of Surgeons, 2017). This work continued until 1950, when a number of other prestigious physicians organizations and the American Hospital Association joined the ACS in establishing the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Hospitals (The Joint Commission, 2017). Today, The Joint Commission (TJC) serves as the premier oversight and accreditation organization for hospitals, clinics and laboratories. Its evidence-based standards are considered to be the best available for evaluating the structure, processes and outcomes of care provided by hospitals. TJC’s accreditation program is the gold standard for excellence within the hospital industry (The Joint Commission, 2017).

The Institute for Healthcare Improvement and the *Triple Aim*

As the healthcare industry continually strives to improve the care services it delivers to meet and exceed standards such as those promulgated by TJC, many consulting and improvement bodies have been formed to provide assistance. The IHI is an organization exclusively dedicated to the enhancement of quality in the nation’s healthcare system. The IHI was developed by Donald Berwick who, with several other colleagues, envisioned a U.S. healthcare system that would function “without errors, waste, delay and unsustainable costs” (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017a, p.

1). This thinking was later translated into IHI's Triple Aim, which has been nationally embraced throughout the U.S. healthcare system as a framework for quality improvement (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017, p. 1). Specifically, the Triple Aim focuses on improving health outcomes, cutting costs and enhancing the patient experience with the healthcare system. To assist in achieving the goals inherent in the Triple Aim, IHI works with many healthcare organizations to undertake improvement efforts using techniques that engage staff at all organizational levels in identifying, structuring and undertaking change.

The Influence of the Institute of Medicine

In 1999, the Committee on the Quality of Health Care in America, appointed under the auspices of the Institute of Medicine (IOM) issued its seminal report *To Err is Human: Building a Safer Health System*. This important work identified goals and strategies for improving the overall safety of America's healthcare system (Institute of Medicine, 1999). The second report of the Committee issued in 2001, *Crossing the Quality Chasm: A New Health System for the 21st Century*, expanded the original work and set forth a set of principles and recommendations for redesigning the U.S. healthcare system, the way healthcare professionals practice and the structures and processes that are needed to provide care (Institute of Medicine, 2001). The report identifies six key aims for redesigning the U.S. healthcare system. These aims focus on healthcare system safety, effectiveness, patient-centeredness, timeliness, efficiency and equitability (Institute of Medicine, 2001). Importantly, the report states that the systems for healthcare delivery in the U.S. "must facilitate the application of scientific knowledge to

practice and provide clinicians with the tools and supports necessary to deliver evidence-based care consistently and safely” (Institute of Medicine, 2001, p. 8).

The IOM report emphasizes the Lean Management premise that unnecessary waste should be removed from all aspects of the U.S. healthcare system. It further asserts that information should be provided to staff, patients and the public as to the system’s performance related to “safety, evidence-based practice and patient satisfaction” (Institute of Medicine, 2001, p. 8). Finally, the report emphasizes the need for all healthcare systems to support the involvement of front-line healthcare teams as they undertake improvement efforts.

The importance of involving staff at all levels is a recurring theme when examining key factors that influence successful healthcare improvement. This issue has been reaffirmed in many studies. For example, in a recent study designed to identify success factors for achieving the six IOM aims (Wang, Hyun, Harrison, Shortell, & Fraser, 2017), sixteen systems redesign experts were interviewed. The interviews were focused on soliciting their viewpoints as to the most important factors that needed to be present for successful healthcare improvement. Staff involvement was consistently mentioned as being essential.

Recognizing Excellence in Quality Improvement

With the robust clinical information systems currently available throughout the healthcare industry, individual facilities can benchmark their services against other agencies to support their quality improvement efforts. In choosing the facilities for their benchmarking, many agencies seek healthcare agencies that have been awarded The Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award in Health Care (National Institute of

Standards and Technology, 2017). The Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award was developed with the active involvement of Edward Juran (British Library, n.d.-a). Established by the U.S. Congress in 1987, the award initially was developed to recognize companies that had distinguished themselves by the manner in which they embraced continuous quality improvement (American Society for Quality, 2017a). In 2002, the award was expanded to include a category specific to health care. Recipients of the award represent some of the most progressive hospitals and healthcare entities in the nation. These healthcare systems now serve as quality improvement benchmarks for others and are frequently visited by colleagues throughout the nation to learn of their approaches. The prestigious Baldrige award is sought by many healthcare systems as it recognizes high-level attainment of excellence. Significantly, the Baldrige award, in its review criteria, focuses on those healthcare organizations that have incorporated their customers (patients), staff and leaders into all quality activities (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2013).

Summary of Healthcare Performance and Quality Improvement

In summarizing performance and quality improvement efforts in the healthcare industry, the same key themes continue to appear as previously described in earlier industrial engineering approaches. Namely, successful efforts are characterized by the inclusion of staff (particularly front-line staff) and recipients of care, systematic and systemic approaches, assurance that improvement efforts will be ongoing, staff and consumer feedback, transparency and, the use of evaluative metrics. The six aims for redesigning the U.S. healthcare system outlined by the IOM as well as IHI's Triple Aim

goals provide direction for performance and quality improvement that are nationally embraced.

Robust databases are now available through such organizations as the National Committee for Quality Assurance (NCQA) and the National Quality Forum (NQF). These databases are becoming more sophisticated and more widely used to support healthcare providers in measuring, evaluating and comparing the care they provide to that provided by others. Importantly, consumers of care can also access these databases to enhance their ability to make informed choices when selecting care. There is also an ever-increasing mandate to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of care delivery. These influences challenge those providing healthcare services to continually seek evidence-based approaches for enhancing quality, cost-effectiveness, and the satisfaction of staff at all levels and, especially, the satisfaction of those served.

Performance and Quality Improvement in Nursing

Today's approaches to the improvement of performance and quality in nursing can be traced to the work undertaken by Florence Nightingale in the 1850s. One of Nightingale's major contributions during and following the Crimean war was the improvement of sanitation and the overall hygiene in hospitals providing care to wounded soldiers. She achieved this by developing a systematic approach to observing clinical situations, collecting data, statistically analyzing those data and developing corrective interventions; much like what nurses do today as they assess care quality and undertake care improvement (Lee, Clark, & Thompson, 2013). She also spoke about the importance of providing data feedback that was clear, understandable and credible to

those she attempted to influence. In this regard, she is cited as developing what is today referred to as the pie chart (Cherry & Jacob, 2017).

Measuring Quality Nursing Care: The Nursing Minimum Data Set

From Nightingale's pioneering work, there were some efforts to focus on improving the quality of nursing care in the early parts of the 20th century however, the major strides toward the development of today's approaches to quality improvement in nursing began in the 1970s. During the 1970s, the nursing profession began to focus on the measurement of clinical outcomes (Jones, 2016). The same pressures and dynamics described in the previous section relating to healthcare in general also impacted and stimulated this effort in nursing. There was a growing need to collect data to demonstrate the relationships between the quality of care provided by nurses and the costs associated with that care.

Nurses represent the largest segment of the healthcare workforce and significantly contribute to the costs associated with care delivery. Nurses then are particularly vulnerable when cost-reduction efforts are undertaken since there have traditionally been no specific metrics to demonstrate nursing's value. There has consequently been more pressure on the nursing profession to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of nursing care and the direct relationship between the provision of care and positive patient outcomes.

In the early 1980s, the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) funded studies to develop *minimum data sets* for assessing healthcare quality in response to healthcare insurer concerns about escalating costs (Hobbs, 2011). Minimum data sets are defined as the least amount of data necessary to evaluate a particular service (Department of Health and Human Services, 1978). It was believed that if data were

collected and analyzed using such data sets, it would be possible to identify healthcare organizations that demonstrated positive cost/outcome relationships. DHHS believed that understanding these relationships and the ability to identify facilities that had high quality/low cost ratios would stimulate improvements in the overall healthcare system. Moreover, they believed that best practices in this regard could be shared with less-performing organizations.

In 1985, Norma Lang and Harriet Werley from the University of Wisconsin received funding from DHHS to develop a Nursing Minimum Data Set (NMDS). They invited a group of influential nurse executives and educators from across the country to join a work group to develop the NMDS. The original goal of the NMDS effort was to identify clinical metrics that were unique to the provision of nursing care. Lang and Werley believed that if such metrics could be identified, data could be collected to demonstrate nursing value.

Unfortunately, at the outset, there were issues about the focus for the effort. The nurse executives on the work group wanted the data set to “account for nursing care delivery” while the nurse educators wanted the data set for researching the “clinical activities of nurses” (Hobbs, 2011, p. 131). Another issue was that nurses on the work group had divergent opinions as to what was important for measuring nursing processes and the impact of nursing care. Without a common focus and consensus as to how nursing practice should be measured, the group struggled in their efforts. While a report was generated and submitted, the DHHS made the decision to take no action. This decision was largely based on the fact that the work did not clearly identify nurse-specific indicators that could be utilized for assessing the quality of care provided by nurses.

The Development of Nursing-Sensitive Indicators

Though the development of a NMDS was not totally successful, there remained the need to define evaluative data specific to nursing to assist in measuring the quality of care provided by nurses and quantify nursing's contributions to care delivery. During the 1990s, social and policy issues in healthcare had a major focus on cost and quality. Many theorized that the most effective way to reduce healthcare costs was to reduce the amount of care provided (Maas, Johnson, & Moorhead, 1996). The primary dilemma in this regard was deciding what services could be safely eliminated and/or modified without compromising care quality and patient safety. While there were efforts to conduct outcomes research to deal with this dilemma, most of the research-related metrics were physician-focused. Nurse leaders were understandably concerned that if research data were predominantly focused on care provided by physicians, nursing's contributions to healthcare would be largely minimized (Maas et al., 1996). Therefore, a renewed effort emerged to develop metrics that were sensitive to the care provided by nurses.

Much of the initial work in developing nursing-sensitive indicators was undertaken at the University of Iowa, College of Nursing. The effort, undertaken in the mid-1990s, focused on classification of nursing-sensitive outcomes (Maas et al., 1996). Over 4,500 patient outcomes statements were collected from a variety of sources and researchers undertook the work of categorizing those statements into groups based upon the degree of linkage between patient outcomes and the care provided by nurses. The groupings were validated through the use of expert panels of nurse clinicians (Maas et al., 1996).

From this initial classification of nursing-sensitive outcomes, there has been ongoing research to refine the outcomes into specific nursing-sensitive indicators (Gallagher & Rowell, 2003). These efforts have led to developing clear data definitions and metrics that can be utilized for assessing outcomes and linking outcomes to nursing care. There has also been work to develop nursing-sensitive indicators that are specific to particular patient populations receiving care in a variety of settings such as ambulatory care, long-term care, rehabilitation, acute care, maternal-child care, and others.

Summary of Nursing Performance Improvement Efforts

In summary, nursing performance improvement and the identification of performance metrics specific to nursing are complex. Nursing plays a pivotal role in healthcare delivery, yet the actual practice of nursing is somewhat difficult to quantify due to the interrelatedness of the nursing role to that of the roles of other healthcare clinicians. Through the development of nursing-sensitive indicators, it is becoming possible to evaluate the effects of nursing care in a new way and even formulate cost/quality relationships related to the provision of nursing care. Ongoing refinement of nursing-specific metrics will become even more essential for documentation and evaluation of nursing's contributions and value as the U.S. healthcare system is becoming increasingly more quality oriented, transparent, patient-centric and cost-efficient.

Healthcare Transparency and Accountability

As the nursing profession has been able to identify nursing-specific indicators to assess care and nursing's contributions to patient outcomes, the overall healthcare industry has similarly developed metrics to demonstrate value associated with various healthcare interventions. As a result, the healthcare system can embrace higher levels of

transparency in the way it operates, the quality of care it provides and the costs associated with care outcomes. This new level of consumer accountability is possible because of the ever-improving metrics and the development of national data repositories that support comparative analyses.

Quality Metrics for the U.S. Healthcare System

Early work to identify the healthcare outcome metrics just mentioned were largely undertaken by interested healthcare researchers working independently of each other (NCQA, 2017b). Importantly, it was learned that to meet the public demand for accountability, there needed to be common metrics for use across the healthcare system to clearly and empirically demonstrate system effectiveness. These metrics were not discipline-specific in nature but more focused on how the healthcare system and the entities providing care were performing.

In 1990, the National Committee for Quality Assurance (NCQA), an independent not-for-profit organization, was formed with the goal of measuring and improving the quality of healthcare delivery throughout the nation (NCQA, 2017a). One of NCQA's first endeavors was the development of a set of metrics that could be used in the overall evaluation of care. These metrics were incorporated into the *Healthcare Effectiveness Data and Information Set* (HEDIS) that is widely utilized today. The 2017 HEDIS measures have over 100 specific metrics categorized under sets of guidelines for Effectiveness of Care, Accessibility of Care, Utilization and Risk-Adjusted Utilization, and Health Plan Descriptive Information (NCQA, 2017c).

Hospitals, health plans, physicians and other providers input HEDIS-identified data pertinent to the care they provide and NCQA develops report cards that allow them

to compare their care and patient outcomes with other similar facilities. NCQA also has accreditation, certification and recognition programs that allow consumers and others to identify healthcare providers that are high performing (NCQA, 2017a). HEDIS measures are now widely utilized throughout the U.S. healthcare system to demonstrate accountability for the provision of quality care. When these data are combined with healthcare costing data, comparisons of cost and quality can be undertaken.

HEDIS measures are frequently utilized to compare care delivery and cost. As the U.S. healthcare system is transitioning to paying entities delivering care based on their performance and quality, HEDIS measures serve as key variables in many studies. For example, a recent study conducted to determine how the socioeconomic factors present within given communities impacted the outcomes of care, showed a “strong and significant” relationship between sociodemographic characteristics and achievement of positive health outcomes as measured by HEDIS performance (Hu, Schreiber, Jordan, George, & Nerenz, 2017, p. 6).

Another organization similar to NCQA is the National Quality Forum (NQF), which was also chartered in 1999. The NQF develops metrics for the assessment of care quality and generates comparative reports in much the same manner as NCQA. Additionally, the NQF has healthcare information technology initiatives to support the development of electronic medical records. It also provides resources for healthcare decision makers in its efforts to improve care quality (National Quality Forum, 2017).

Databases for Nursing Sensitive Indicators

Though the metrics just described are relatively sophisticated, they typically are not discipline-specific and have not addressed the issues being faced by the nursing

profession in terms of the value and costs associated with the provision of nursing care in relationship to patient outcomes.

In 1994, the American Nurses Association (ANA) provided funding to develop a report card that was specific to care provided by nurses in the acute care setting (Rowell & Milholland, 1998). The primary concern at the time was to demonstrate nursing's impact on patient safety and care quality. From this initial effort, state nursing associations in Arizona, California, North Dakota and Texas were funded to partner with institutions providing clinical services to obtain data and test a number of quality indicators that were believed to be significantly influenced by nurses (Rowell & Milholland, 1998).

The following year, ANA contracted with a consulting firm to conduct an analysis of health-related data associated with nursing processes and adverse patient events in six areas: (1) pressure injuries, (2) nosocomial infections, (3) post-operative infections, (4) urinary tract infections, (5) pneumonia, and (6) patient falls (Rowell & Milholland, 1998). This analysis proved fruitful and, from this work, a number of nursing-sensitive metrics were identified.

With the formulation of nursing-sensitive indicators, a new level of sophistication for assessing nursing's impact within the healthcare system emerged. The new measures could, for the first time, be used for comparative analyses of nursing impact throughout the healthcare system. They could also be used to benchmark care delivery with other like facilities and even patient care units within the same facility. Importantly, through such analyses, a better understanding of the relationship between the costs for providing nursing care and quality could be identified (Gallagher & Rowell, 2003).

To conduct such analyses, there emerged the need for national data support and the ANA developed the National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators (NDNQI) to meet this need. The NDNQI was established in 1998 as a data repository where facility-specific data relating to nursing-sensitive indicators could be stored, analyzed and made available for comparative analyses (Montalvo, 2007). On a quarterly basis, healthcare facilities submitted nurse staffing, patient outcome and patient satisfaction data that were specific to the facility's discrete organizational units. Nursing-sensitive indicators developed by the ANA as well as the National Quality Form were utilized as hospitals contributed their data. In turn, NDNQI analyzed the data and developed facility-specific reports.

In 2014 the NDNQI database was purchased from the ANA by Press Ganey, a nationally recognized firm specializing in improvement of the patient experience within the healthcare industry (Press Ganey, 2015). Through this acquisition, the amount and type of data available for evaluation of nursing care has significantly increased, and it is now possible to obtain reports that contain data relating to nursing-sensitive indicators as well as the patient satisfaction associated with nursing care delivery.

Another organization providing data specific to nursing-sensitive indicators is the Collaborative Alliance for Nursing Outcomes (CALNOC). CALNOC was one of the pilot sites working with ANA in the development of nursing-sensitive indicators as ANA developed the NDNQI database (Collaborative Alliance for Nursing Outcomes, 2017). CALNOC also is a developer of nursing-sensitive indicators for the NQF and today provides data services for nine states. Many hospitals and healthcare agencies in California report their data into both the NDNQI and CALNOC databases and can

consequently generate reports from both organizations. While there are commonalities in the two databases, there is enough difference in the metrics used in the two databases to make dual reporting beneficial.

The Important Role of Feedback

From the early work of Deming and Juran to the contemporary healthcare improvement approaches undertaken by the IHI, four key components necessary for positive organizational improvement emerge: (1) Development of organizational metrics, (2) auditing performance, (3) performance feedback and (4) involvement of front line staff in each of these activities. As described in the previous discussion, without the involvement of those actively engaged in service delivery, attempts at performance improvement many times fail or, at least, do not reach their full potential (Wang et al., 2017).

When appropriate metrics are developed to assess care quality, care outcomes are audited and feedback is provided to those involved in care delivery and improvement occurs. A recent study conducted at an acute care hospital in Norway demonstrates how such audit and feedback improved overall adherence to antibiotic prescribing guidelines (Høgli, Garcia, Skjold, Skogen, & Småbrekke, 2016). Physicians providing care in the respiratory unit were given feedback from an audit of clinical records. They were also furnished with pocket cards outlining the guidelines for antibiotic therapy. Following the feedback, there was a 22.1% increase in appropriate prescribing of antibiotics.

Similarly, a study conducted at the University of Geneva Hospitals in Switzerland demonstrated a relationship between providing feedback to staff and quality care improvement (Stewardson et al., 2016). This study focused on hand hygiene. In the

randomized trial, wards were assigned to one of three groups: “(1) control, (2) enhanced performance feedback, and (3) enhanced performance feedback with patient participation” (Stewardson et al., 2016, p. 1). Two evidence-based interventions were designed. The first, enhanced performance feedback, consisted of setting a goal for hand hygiene compliance (80%), observing actual performance and providing immediate feedback. The second intervention expanded on the first by educating patients as to appropriate hand hygiene and advising them to ask staff who had not done so to wash their hands before touching them. The study demonstrates an overall hand hygiene performance improvement of 9% (from 65% to 74%) as a result of the feedback.

Simply providing feedback has been shown to improve overall quality of care, however other studies demonstrate that the way feedback is provided can also significantly impact performance improvement. The U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs (VA) has been a leader in establishing performance metrics, collecting clinical performance data and providing feedback to those in administrative oversight roles and to clinicians providing care. While VA has conducted many studies to demonstrate the importance of feedback on clinical care improvement, a recent VA study was aimed at examining how the manner in which performance feedback is provided also impacts improvement (Ross, Williams, Damush, & Matthias, 2016).

Qualitative interviews were conducted at 12 VA hospitals targeted toward feedback associated with provision of care for stroke patients. Specifically, physicians, nurses and hospital leaders were interviewed to ascertain their perception of feedback they had received regarding a national report on the quality of care provided to acute

stroke patients. The facility-specific data received were comparative in nature offering opportunity to benchmark with VA facilities across the nation.

Several key findings associated with the study offer important perspective relative to the concept of performance feedback. Feedback was generally perceived as positively impacting patient care and stimulating to individual improvement when it was meaningful to the individual and pertinent to their work. There was concern expressed as to the timeliness of feedback with staff conveying that old data were not terribly useful. Validity of data and perceived soundness of methodologies for performance measurement were also addressed in the study. When data validity or the metrics for evaluation is questioned, staff are less receptive of feedback. Data overload was also identified as a contributing factor to negative feedback receptivity. Finally, the study emphasized that if feedback is provided in a positive, non-punitive manner it can be a positive morale booster and validation that one's care delivery approach has been effective (Ross et al., 2016).

Confirming and expanding upon the results of the VA study, a meta-analysis was conducted to review studies relating to how auditing of performance and providing feedback to healthcare providers relates to the provision of quality care (Hysong, 2009). Of 519 studies initially identified, a mere 19 met the inclusion criteria due to the exclusion of studies where both auditing and feedback were not addressed. An overarching finding was that feedback needs to be targeted. Generalized feedback was shown not to be as effective as feedback specific to individuals, the work they perform and the "outcomes of interest" to them (Hysong, 2009, p. 7). Feedback also needs to be non-punitive in nature. If negative actions are taken when performance is not at desired

levels, it is not generally well received and could, in fact, contribute to degradation in performance. Feedback also needs to be frequent and ideally in writing versus offered verbally or even graphically. Finally, feedback accompanied with information as to solutions for resolving poor performance was perceived as highly important in the studies included in the meta-analysis.

In summary, positive, targeted feedback can stimulate performance improvement and can serve to motivate those providing care to engage in continuous improvement activities. If feedback is positively received, nurses and others can engage in identifying evidence-based interventions to address quality deficiencies and even further strengthen those care interventions that are working well.

Strategies for Effective Feedback

As the prior discussion demonstrates, feedback is highly important to the delivery and continual improvement of patient care. The studies just summarized provide important guidance relating to how feedback should be provided. However, what is also important is that there is a well-defined communication strategy so that the method and style of feedback assures that it is ongoing and timely as opposed to sporadic. The tools used for communicating performance also need to be carefully developed with the input of staff who will be receiving the feedback so that they are positively perceived, clear and effective in communicating what is truly important and actionable. In this regard, feedback tools can range from simply communicating raw data to sophisticated dashboards, report cards and programs that incorporate principles of visual management. Ideally, a combination of multiple feedback mechanisms should be utilized to assure optimal communication in consideration of staff diversity.

Report Cards and Dashboards

One mechanism frequently used to communicate information related to care quality is the report card. Report cards can be provider, hospital, program or unit-specific. They can also be individualized for specific providers. For example, a prospective study was conducted at Johns Hopkins Medical Center related to providing performance feedback to surgical residents relative to the appropriateness of their prescribing of prophylaxis for venous thromboembolism (VTE). Monthly resident-specific report cards were generated to inform residents as to the appropriateness of their ordering practices. When the report card intervention was initiated, the risk-appropriate VTE ordering increased from 59.8% to 88% (Lau et al., 2016).

Another mechanism popularly utilized to share quality of care data with staff is the dashboard. Dashboards are similar to report cards except they typically contain more data and data are displayed in a manner to support comparison. The comparisons can demonstrate performance over time or show performance in relation to other benchmark providers, units or facilities. Dashboards are also typically constructed in a manner that is easily readable and interpretable, allowing the person viewing the data to quickly focus on that information that is most significant within the data set. For example, the Southern Ohio Medical Center has developed unit-specific dashboards that color-code data so that staff can easily see which performance measures are meeting pre-identified targets and which require further improvement (Health Leaders Media, 2009). Unit-specific dashboards tie to nursing-wide dashboards and they, in turn, tie to hospital-wide dashboards that provide key information relating to overall hospital performance.

There are on-line dashboard generating programs that can be used to customize and visualize data in a manner that engages those involved in performance/quality improvement. However, incorporating dashboards into the performance improvement program in a nursing service is not an easy task because there is rarely time set aside for receiving performance information, digesting it and developing improvement interventions. The day-to-day workload in a typical nursing unit is unpredictable and usually fast-paced. Even when time is specifically set aside for meetings and/or reviewing data, last-minute emergencies may occur which supersede quality improvement efforts

In a qualitative study conducted in Toronto, Canada, front-line nurses and nurse leaders were interviewed to ascertain their perceptions as to barriers for implementation of dashboards. The key barriers they identified related to the lack of time that leaders and staff nurses had to analyze data and develop corrective actions. Recommendations emanating from this study focused on the need for a coordinated approach involving nurse leaders, educators and staff nurses in creating the type of environment on each unit where such review and action is valued and supported (Jeffs et al., 2014). This perspective is shared by St Pierre (2006) who, in her article *Staff Nurses' Use of Report Card Data for Quality Improvement: First Steps*, relates the complaint that "limited resources and heavy workloads reduce them [nurses] to being task-oriented, thereby limiting their ability to provide quality care." St Pierre also states that "nurses do not always know when they have or have not provided quality care." (St Pierre, 2006, p. 8). Despite these comments, she asserts that feedback on the quality of care provided by nurses makes their work more meaningful.

Frazier and Williams (2012), two nurse leaders at St. Vincent Health System in Little Rock, AR, indicated that they utilized nursing dashboards to ‘hard wire the concept of nursing-driven quality within the organization’ (Frazier & Williams, 2012, p. 4). The concept of hard wiring is related to the goal that many organizations have of developing a nursing organization that is exemplified by a culture of quality.

In summary, the use of nursing dashboards can be very effective in providing feedback to front-line nursing staff. However, to be effective, they need to be designed for ease in reading and interpretation and time needs to be specifically set aside for staff to engage in discussion as to the meaning of the data and identification of interventions targeted to improve performance.

Visual Management

Another strategy and set of tools for communicating data related to quality and performance improvement are encompassed in the concept of Visual Management (VM). VM relates to incorporating visualization techniques into the workplace in a manner that assists organizations to continually improve their quality and achieve corporate objectives (Liff & Posey, 2004). This is different from simply providing data through dashboards. VM ties together the overall philosophy and goals of the organization with organizational aims so that employees are continually informed as to progress and motivated to take actions to achieve corporate priorities.

VM can take many forms such as printed materials, real-time planning boards, television monitors that show the status of activities, workplace computer screen updates and many others. The main goal for VM is to constantly put forth information using visualizations that stimulate desired employee action. For example, Bititci, Cocca &

Ates (2015) conducted explorative action research in seven companies where “visual performance management systems” were implemented as an intervention (Bititci, Cocca, & Ates, 2015, p. 1574). The attributes of the companies prior to the intervention were documented and specific outcomes following interventions in each of the seven companies were described. In all cases, there were dramatically positive outcomes following the incorporation of VM techniques. For example, one company based in Ireland, had no real strategic direction, no performance measures and no operational metrics before implantation. The company was described as “struggling to survive” due to the 2009-2010 global recession (Bititci et al., 2015, p. 1584). Following implementation of VM, the company had the opportunity to view itself in a way that pointed toward the need for diversification and, as a result, experienced new corporate growth.

An exploratory study was conducted in Spain to identify the “actual state of VM tools/techniques in real life companies” (Jaca, Viles, Jurburg, & Tanco, 2014, p. 1759). The researchers utilized a model published in a 1991 classic text on VM titled *The Visual Factory* to develop classification criteria for assessing how engaged companies were in VM. The classification schema included twenty categories that were believed to be indicative of the presence of VM. The categories were useful in describing some of the concrete ways that organizations visually operate and provide feedback to their staff and customers. Key attributes identified related to a company’s displaying corporate objectives, results and deviation from goals/objectives; creating visibility for improvement activities and the actions taken to make improvements; and visually displaying the corporate mission, vision and values (Jaca et al., 2014).

Given the complexity of the programs and services provided by nursing in most healthcare organizations, VM could provide an important tool for keeping staff focused on what is important to the organization and keeping patients informed as to the organization's performance in relationship to other similar organizations.

Summary

In summary, it is highly important for every healthcare facility to incorporate the concept of continuous quality improvement into every aspect of its operations. Nowhere is this more important than in continually assessing the quality of direct care services provided and the way those services impact the health outcomes of patients. As previously mentioned, quality and performance improvement involve developing metrics to evaluate the structural components of the organization as well as its processes and the outcomes it hopes to achieve for those it serves. Once these metrics are developed, ongoing assessment can be undertaken to validate organizational performance and identify areas where improvement is necessary.

As the studies included in this literature review reveal, it is highly important that performance and quality of care feedback be provided to staff at all levels and that they be fully involved in interpreting data and designing improvement interventions. It is particularly important for nurses and members of the nursing staff to be engaged in these improvement efforts due to their direct and intimate interface with patients. Nurses have a major impact on the patient's optimal healing, the outcomes of care provided and the safety of those served. The lessons learned from the studies included in this review of literature served as an important backdrop and reference as the project was developed and implemented at Rancho.

METHODS

The primary focus for this DNP quality improvement project was to improve the pathways necessary to communicate NSI performance data to staff nurses. A methodology for achieving this goal was developed and piloted on two selected nursing units at Rancho. From the outset of the project, it was hoped that introduction of such a methodology could serve as a beneficial tool to provide staff nurses with timely and consistent data relating to the quality of care they provide.

Setting

Rancho is a prominent, 395-bed treatment center for patients who have experienced catastrophic health events for which they need specialized care and rehabilitation services. Inpatients are admitted to one of nine nursing units depending on their specialty need. The Rancho Department of Nursing's approach to nursing care delivery is patient-centered and grounded in evidence-based practice (Rancho Los Amigos Department of Nursing, 2017). Data are routinely collected relative to the satisfaction of patients, staffing effectiveness and organizational performance related to nationally-recognized quality of care metrics and NSIs, such as pressure injuries and falls.

Study Population

The study population were nurse leaders and staff nurses providing care on two nursing units at Rancho. For the purposes of this study, two 25-bed units were selected for piloting the data dissemination methodology, a Direct Observation (ICU step-down) Unit and a unit providing rehabilitation care for stroke patients. These two units were selected because they represented the two general types of nursing units at Rancho, acute

care and specialty rehabilitation. These units also admitted patients with differing diagnoses and risk profiles associated with a number of NSIs.

The nursing staffs on these two units were similar in terms of size (approximately 35 registered nurses on each unit) and their educational backgrounds. Roughly fifty percent of the staff nurses were baccalaureate prepared and the other half were prepared at the associate degree level. Most of the nurses on the rehabilitation unit were nationally certified Rehabilitation Nurses while those assigned to the step-down unit had specialized training and certification in Advanced Cardiac Life Support.

Ethical Issues

No patients were involved in the project. Though results from questionnaires completed by staff and findings associated with the project were shared as appropriate throughout the Department of Nursing, nursing staff were not individually identified. An Institutional Review Board (IRB) application was submitted to the Rancho Los Amigos IRB as well as to the IRB at California State University, Long Beach. The project was formally reviewed by both IRBs and approved through expedited review.

The Quality Improvement Intervention

Rancho has been internally collecting and summarizing data related to NSIs for some time and has reported data related to hospital-acquired pressure injuries into the database maintained by CALNOC. Recently data related to patient falls has also been reported to CALNOC and pressure injury data has begun being uploaded into the database maintained by NDNQI. It is Rancho's desire to expand reporting to these data repositories so that ongoing benchmarking can be more effectively undertaken.

The intervention involved designing and implementing data dashboards to communicate quality of care data to staff nurses employed on the two pilot units. To facilitate the process for developing the desired dashboards, several dashboard examples that were reported in the literature were presented to nurse executives and the QSOC. The sample dashboards were then critiqued and desirable and less desirable attributes of each were identified. From this analysis, the QSOC members identified four key themes that should be included on each dashboard: (1) graphic images and wording to tie the dashboards to the shared governance process, the Department of Nursing's transformational efforts and the work of the QSOC, (2) graphs and charts to pictorially present data in a manner to foster understanding, (3) general information to guide staff in data interpretation and (4) suggested questions that could be utilized by unit Colabs and nurse managers as they discussed the quality of care feedback with their staffs.

Based on this feedback, dashboards were created and distributed to the two pilot units at the beginning of the month for three consecutive months. Each month's dashboard was critically assessed by unit Colab members and members of the QSOC and their suggestions for improvement were incorporated when subsequent monthly dashboards were created.

The November Dashboard

Because there was a wealth of data related to hospital-acquired pressure injuries and an all-patient pressure injury surveillance study had recently been completed, nurse executives and members of the QSOC decided that the first dashboard should contain unit-specific data focused on pressure injuries. The first dashboard was developed and displayed on the units in November (Appendix B). It contained two data graphs, one

showing the total number of patients on the unit compared to the number of patients deemed to be at high risk for developing pressure injuries and the other showing the unit's performance in implementing Rancho's *SKIN Bundle* over four consecutive quarters.

The December Dashboard

Since the November dashboard contained pressure injury data that were internally generated, the QSOC decided that the December dashboard (Appendix C) should contain data that would permit external benchmarking utilizing the CALNOC database.

Comparative data were downloaded and displayed to show Rancho's performance in relationship to the performance of all other CALNOC facilities reporting data on pressure injuries. Comparative data were displayed for each quarter over the past year.

The January Dashboard

At the request of the QSOC, the January dashboard (Appendix D) presented data specific to patient satisfaction with nursing care. Data were downloaded from the patient satisfaction database maintained by Press Ganey. The dashboard contained two graphs, one comparing how Rancho ranked in comparison to three benchmark groups over five consecutive quarters. The three benchmark/peer groups were: (1) All hospitals in the Press Ganey database (national peer group), (2) all California hospitals in the database and (3) teaching hospitals with over 100 beds. Each bar in the graph represents how Rancho compared to that comparison group. For example, in the first chart in the dashboard shown in Appendix D, Rancho's ranked above 80% of the hospitals in the national comparison group. Conversely, 20% of the hospitals in the group ranked higher than Rancho.

The second chart contained in the January dashboard showed how Rancho ranked on each of the six nursing-specific questions contained on the Press Ganey survey for the third quarter of 2017. This quarter was chosen because the data demonstrated a decrease in patient satisfaction during that quarter and it was believed that more in-depth analysis of data for the third quarter would be illustrative.

Methods of Evaluation

The project was evaluated in three ways. A five-question survey instrument was developed specifically for the project (Appendix A). The questions contained on the survey were related to similar questions that were being piloted by NDNQI in their Annual RN Survey relating to the manner and level in which staff nurses were engaged in receiving and reviewing quality of care data. The questions and overall survey instrument were reviewed by members of the QSOC and revisions were made based on this feedback. The questionnaire was subsequently administered to all staff nurses on the two pilot units prior to beginning the study and again following the three-month implementation. Data obtained from pre and post-study questionnaires were entered into an excel spreadsheet and data entry was checked for accuracy by comparing questionnaire responses to the actual data entry three times. In entering the data, scores were assigned to possible responses to each question as follow: Never = 1, Rarely = 2, Sometimes = 3, Frequently = 4 and Always = 5. By assigning numerical values to responses, it was possible to better compare between pre and post-study results.

Nursing units were then visited by the PI during the three-month project implementation. Units were observed to ascertain the actual physical presence of the

dashboards and minutes of unit-based Colabs were reviewed to determine if data were being shared and discussed.

Finally, nurse leaders and members of the QSOC and unit-based Colabs were queried as to their perceptions of the effectiveness of the dashboards in communicating data to staff nurses. These discussions focused on whether the dashboards were providing an effective tool for data dissemination, if the level of sophistication for data display was appropriate, and whether it was believed that the dashboards should be continued.

RESULTS

Results from the Pre and Post-Implementation Questionnaire

Prior to the start of the project, all staff nurses on the two pilot units were surveyed using the questionnaire shown in Appendix A. The questionnaire was again administered to staff nurses at the end of the three-month implementation. Pre and post-study response rates on the step-down unit were equal at 72%. The pre-study response rate on the medical rehabilitation unit was 78% and the post-study rate was 54%.

The pre-study survey demonstrated only slight differences in the two units in four of the questions. The only major difference was in relation to the question about whether nurses received monthly quality reports. Nurses on the step-down unit all indicated that they “always” received the reports while nurses on the rehabilitation unit generally indicated that they “sometimes” received the reports. Responses to the other four questions demonstrated very little difference between the two units. Nurse managers and the QSOC members familiar with the two units expressed their opinion that results seemed to be what they would have suspected, which provided anecdotal confirmation of data accuracy.

Comparisons of post-study results to pre-study responses (Appendix E) did not demonstrate major differences for either of the two units except for the question related to receiving monthly reports. Responses from nurses on the step-down unit indicated that they “always” received the reports in the pre-study survey and in the post-study survey, this changed to their indicating that they “frequently” received monthly reports.

Results from Unit Observations and Reviews of Minutes

While during unit visitations each month it was observed that the dashboards were posted on each of the pilot units, they were, at first, difficult to physically locate. The walls of the units were populated with many postings and memoranda and there was no specifically-designed place for the posting of quality of care data. After the first month, this situation was somewhat resolved when a designated spot on each unit was selected for posting the dashboards, however, as time went by, these areas too were used to post non-quality-related information. It is anticipated that this issue will be resolved in the near future as new display boards specifically designated to communications from Departmental councils are strategically placed on each unit. When installation of the display boards is complete, the dashboards will have a predominate place under communication from the QSOC.

A review of minutes from unit-based Colabs revealed that discussions relating to the dashboards and the data provided therein only occurred on one of the pilot units during the November meeting. However, a discussion of the dashboards was routinely scheduled after that. The quality and length of discussions in this regard were not captured in the minutes. Therefore, it was not possible to assess the depth of these conversations.

Results from Discussions with Nurse Leaders and Council Members

Nurse executives and the nursing leadership team agreed that the dashboards could be helpful in communicating data and fostering care quality improvements throughout the Department. There were, however, a number of discussions with nurse leaders, members of the QSOC and members of the Evidence-Based Practice (EBP)

Council related to the appropriate level of sophistication for data presented in the dashboards. As previously described, the Department of Nursing had recently undertaken an organizational restructuring and, with that restructuring, a *cultural transformation* was taking place to engage all staff nurses in quality improvement efforts. The progress of this transformation varied from one unit to another. It was therefore decided that future dashboards should be developed within the context of each nursing unit's uniqueness and specific needs, beginning with very simple data displays and adding complexity as deemed appropriate to support transformational efforts.

Members of both the QSOC and EBP as well as unit Colab members indicated their belief that the dashboard approach was important, and that their importance would grow as the Department continued in its transformative activities.

DISCUSSION

The key findings from this project demonstrated that data dashboards represented a useful and valuable tool for improving communication pathways related to feedback on nursing-specific quality of care indicators throughout the Department of Nursing. Nurse managers and others charged with governing council responsibilities supported this intervention and expressed that the dashboards would, over time, become even more important in involving staff nurses in quality of care improvement initiatives. It was surprising that staff nurses on the two pilot units did not indicate major differences post project in receiving reports, the availability of the reports on the units, the ease of understanding the reports, discussions of the reports in staff meetings or their overall involvement in quality improvement activities. One of the units (step down) reported that they actually received reports less often post project than pre-implementation of the dashboards. This could be a product of time and better understanding of what constitutes quality-related reports.

These findings are important when considering expanding the data dissemination approach beyond the pilot units and/or for replicating it in other facilities. While there were not major differences in terms of responses to pre and post-project questionnaires, it is probable that this finding may be due to the fact that staff nurses throughout the facility had not had significant prior involvement in receiving quality of care feedback. Likewise, they had not had specific training in data review and analysis. In Colab and QSOC meetings, such learning needs were identified and the EBP Council has begun planning for such educational opportunities.

One issue identified through the project was that before data dissemination methodologies are designed and implemented, it is important to assess the existing level of staff competence in understanding data and metrics typically used to assess care quality. The approach to data dissemination needs to be geared to the knowledge-base of the nursing staff and their experience in receiving, analyzing and acting upon data feedback. For example, if the organizational unit has many nurses educated at advanced practice levels who have been engaged in evidence-based practice activities as a routine part of their practice, the level of sophistication for data dashboards can be high. However, if nurses on the units have had little exposure to data analysis, the dashboards need to be constructed in a manner that offers opportunity for beginning-level data interpretation. As staff competence in data understanding grows, the dashboards can be appropriately modified to gradually increase the level of sophistication.

This project was conducted in a facility where a major restructuring was underway with the goal of better engaging staff nurses in the operational aspects of the Department, particularly in their receiving and acting upon quality of care feedback. While the approach utilized to structure the project and design dashboards included staff nurses functioning on key departmental committees, it is possible that the level of understanding of data and the ability to engage in analysis was at a higher level with these nurses than with other staff nurses on the pilot units. The very fact that nurse executives saw a need for better staff nurse engagement, suggests that such involvement was not optimal. As a result of this, as each iteration of the dashboard was constructed, much more emphasis was placed on staff education, explaining the meaning of data

presented and suggesting questions to consider at the unit level when undertaking quality improvement initiatives.

The ongoing need for staff education as dashboards are generated and presented to staff nurses cannot be underestimated. A formalized staff education program geared toward understanding and acting on quality of care feedback needs to accompany actual data dissemination. Likewise, dedicated time needs to be devoted on each nursing unit for data interpretation and devising care improvement interventions. One study, undertaken at an acute care hospital demonstrated that only 62% of clinical registered nurses were even aware of NSIs and how they could be used to improve care quality (Mangold & Pearson, 2017). The pre and post-project questionnaire results in this project most probably related to the need for staff education to accompany dashboard dissemination. While some education did occur at QSOC and unit-based Colab meetings to facilitate data interpretation, similar education and discussions did not occur on the pilot units involving front-line staff nurses.

Not all nursing units within the facility are the same. Some units may have more nurses prepared at baccalaureate and advanced degree levels while others may have a mix of staff that includes a preponderance of associate degree graduates. Likewise, nurse leaders from different units vary in terms of their ability to set priorities, interpret data and inspire staff toward continuous quality improvement. The nature of the work also varies from one unit to another. Nursing responsibilities, daily pace and time for engagement in quality improvement efforts in an intensive care unit may be quite different from the typical work on a rehabilitation unit. Dashboards and other communication tools need to be developed to support this variation. Stated another way,

unless there is total uniformity within a nursing department, which would be a rarity, any thought of developing the same dashboard for all units, while easier, would not be effective in achieving staff engagement.

Any effort to enhance data dissemination needs to also be undertaken within the framework of the organizational model utilized by the nursing department. The approach to data dissemination will, of necessity, be very different in a department that has a more traditional, hierarchical structure with centralized decision making than one that is decentralized. A more centralized structure typically engages nurses at the leadership level in organizational decision making and quality of care review while decentralized structures tend to support maximum involvement of nurses throughout the department.

Another issue relates to the availability of dedicated resources to support ongoing development and operationalization of quality of care feedback mechanisms such as dashboards. Staff need to be specifically identified to collect and summarize data, upload data to national data repositories and generate and distribute reports and dashboards. This can be exceedingly time consuming and the need for resources will vary depending upon the level of information technology available within the organization. For example, some nursing departments have only recently converted to automated Medical Information Systems (MIS) and/or have very rudimentary systems while others have robust systems that have been in use for many years. Clearly, if data are automatically captured through the normal processes of care delivery (as is possible with most MIS systems) the data-related workload will be substantially less than if data are collected manually.

Finally, true engagement in quality of care improvement in most nursing departments requires some redesign of administrative and clinical systems. It is very difficult to simply absorb data analysis and care improvement activities into the already task-heavy care delivery environment. Unless workflow and systems are modified to provide the time necessary to adequately collect, review, interpret and discuss data and design meaningful, evidence-based interventions, staff will experience levels of frustration that may preclude their meaningful involvement. Therefore, existing work structures and staff expectations need to be reviewed and redesigned. Such systems redesign needs to be undertaken using methodologies designed for systematically reviewing existing systems, identifying opportunities to eliminate unnecessary tasks that provide little value and identifying mechanisms for incorporating new activities in an effective and efficient manner.

As demonstrated through this project, data dashboards can provide an effective tool for communicating quality of care data to the unit level. However, dashboard development and implementation is an iterative process where prototypes are continually developed and tested and where sophistication grows as the organization changes. It must be kept in mind that dashboards function merely as tools for data dissemination. For true quality improvement to occur, front-line staff nurses need to understand the feedback provided in the dashboards and continually engage in identifying interventions to enhance quality. As demonstrated in the study previously described relating to implementation of LEAN management as a tool for improving patient satisfaction, simply implementing the tool without patient involvement had little impact on patient satisfaction (Poksinska et al., 2017). Similarly, implementing dashboards as a tool for

improving the quality of care provided by staff nurses achieves little without accompanying staff education, support in data interpretation and true engagement of those whose care is being assessed.

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APPENDIX A

PRE- AND POST IMPLEMENTATION QUESTIONNAIRE

NURSING STAFF SURVEY

Your Unit:

Please place an "X" in the box that identifies which nursing unit you are working on as you take the survey.

Unit A

Unit B

Statement #1: Nursing Department reports relating to the quality of care provided on my unit are received at least monthly.

Select Choice

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Frequently

Always

Statement #2: Nursing Department quality of care reports are readily available on the unit for me to review when I wish to do so.

Select Choice

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Frequently

Always

Statement #3: When I do see quality of care reports, they are provided in a format that makes them easy to read and understand.

Select Choice

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Frequently

Always

Statement #4: We have discussions in staff meetings on my unit regarding the data provided in the quality of care reports.

Select Choice

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Frequently

Always

Statement #5: When we receive quality of care reports, I am directly involved in improving the care when it is indicated that care could be improved.

Select Choice

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Frequently

Always

APPENDIX B

NOVEMBER DATA DASHBOARD

Rancho Los Amigos Nursing

Quality ~ Safety ~ Outcomes

Pressure Injury Surveillance

Unit A

November 2017 Dashboard

Most Patients on Unit are at Risk For Developing Pressure Injuries

Unit 102 Compliance with SKIN Bundle

S=Support Surface
K=Keep Moving
I=Incontinence
N=Nutrition

Unit-Based Action Items

1. Review/Discuss SKIN Bundle Components Where Lower Compliance Exists
2. Design Intervention Strategies for Low-Performing Components
3. Implement Strategies
4. Conduct Daily Pressure Injury Huddles

APPENDIX C

DECEMBER DATA DASHBOARD

Rancho Los Amigos Nursing

Quality ~ Safety ~ Outcomes

Unit A

December 2017 Dashboard

How Does Rancho Compare to Other Hospitals?

It is possible to compare (benchmark) with other hospitals when:

- ✓ There is similar data reported
 - ✓ There is somewhere to send the data
 - ✓ Data are processed to show comparisons
- Rancho sends data to CALNOC
- ✓ Other hospitals also send their data
 - ✓ Rancho can then do comparative reports

Questions for the Unit Collaborative to consider:

1. How does Rancho compare with other hospitals reporting to Pressure Injury data to CALNOC?
2. Is our trend going in the RIGHT direction?
3. How did we do on our unit in identifying strategies for improving compliance with the SKIN bundle?
4. Have we seen a difference with our interventions? If not..what else do we need to do?

**Comparison of Rancho To All Other CALNOC Reporting Hospitals
Hospital-Acquired Pressure Injuries**

APPENDIX D

JANUARY DATA DASHBOARD

Rancho Los Amigos Nursing

Quality ~ Safety ~ Outcomes

All Units
January 2018 Dashboard

Patient Satisfaction With Care Provided by Nurses

Patient Satisfaction With Nursing Care
Rancho Rank In Comparison With Benchmark
Hospitals

Questions To Be Addressed:

- ✓ Are the trends going in the right directions?
- ✓ What happened in Quarter 3--2017?
- ✓ What were actually seeing with our patients during this period?
- ✓ Where are there the biggest opportunities for needed change?

Concepts for Consideration:

- ❖ What is the relationship between patient and staff satisfaction?
- ❖ What are the biggest staff "satisfiers" and "dissatisfiers"?
- ❖ What "systems" were involved and how did they impact results?
- ❖ Is morale a symptom of decreased patient satisfaction or a cause?
(Which comes first—the chicken or the egg?)

Patient Satisfaction With Nursing
Third Quarter 2017

Data Provided by:
 PRESS GANEY

Note: To clarify, all bars in the chart represent Rancho's performance in relation to the three benchmark/peer groups. For example, in quarter 4-16, Rancho ranked better than 80% of the hospitals in the national comparison group. Conversely, 20% of the hospitals in the group ranked higher than Rancho.

APPENDIX E

PRE AND POST STUDY STAFF QUESTIONNAIRE COMPARISONS

APPENDIX F
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1
TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR UNIT-BASED DASHBOARD PROJECT

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Systems/Quality Improvement					
Relationship between a community's sociodemographic status and health outcomes related to HEDIS measures (Hu et al., 2017)	Comparative Analysis Selected HEDIS measures Sociodemographic data from Census 2010-2014 Am Community Survey	22 Clinic sites operated by Henry Ford Health Syst Detroit, MI	HEDIS performance on: 3 Cancer screening 5 Diabetic measures Blood pressure control SDS data on: Household income % Pop ↓ poverty % Pop ↑ HS ed. Employ rate % Afro-Americans	Strong correl between neighborhood SDS and HEDIS Mod correl between process measures where pt. invol (colonoscopy, LDL screening where fasting involved) Poor correl between process measures where pt. not actively involved (blood screening, etc.)	Question as to whether CMS should be using HEDIS measures for HC reimbursement without adjust. For SDS Will be useful in demonstrating the importance of HEDIS in HC research

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Examine success in implementing Healthcare redesigns to achieve IOM six aims (Wang et al., 2017)	Semi-structured telephone interviews Discussion at national experts meeting Literature review	16 HC providers & researchers at organizations involved in SR Nationwide	Obstacles in SR Strategies for overcoming obstacles	Four factors in overcoming SR barriers 1 Involve top/mid-level mgmt. 2 Strategically align improve efforts with org. priorities 3 Systematic estab infrastructure, process and performance appraisal syst for contin improv 4 Devel/involve champions, teams staff Challenge to get HC providers engaged in SR 1 Time	Stresses the need for involvement at all levels Need performance metrics for monitoring progress Complex changes across multiple org layers Need to create urgency Will be useful in supporting need for staff involvement at all org. levels

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
				2 Lack of believe in QA feedback since not resh based 3 Not a priority	
Examines the role of Lean management in relation to impact on patient satis.	Two qualitative and one quantitative study Pt Satis where Lean is practiced vs. control	23 PC centers working with Lean 23 PC centers not (control grp)	How PC organ. define / improve “value” from pt. perspective	Lean primarily impact efficiency vs. pt. satis. No signif difference in pt. satis where Lean used	Lean has little effect on pt. satis unless pt. involved Pt’s perspective should be key to identifying “value” of processes and systems
(Poksinska et al., 2017)	Semi-structured interviews relat to: 1 Perceived definition of Lean 2 Lean tools/tech used 3 Organ of work improve. 4 Results achieved with Lean implementation	15 Interviews Review of organ documents: 1 Strategy docs 2 Activity repts 3 Handling repts 4 Procedures 5 Perf data from past and current Lean activ.	Differences in pt. satis. between PC sites practicing Lean and those not Pt. satis improving over time where Lean practiced	No signif difference in pt. satis over time where Lean used	Value stream analysis needs to include both staff and patient perspectives
		Sweden			Helpful in focus on need to involve pts. and staff in QI

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Design of an instrument to assess an organization's engagement in LEAN management (Roszell & Lynn, 2016)	Four phase instrument development process: 1 Delphi process using LEAN experts to identify and refine key items for assessment 2 Assess content validity and readability of instrument 3 Field testing of instrument North Carolina	Instrument Design conducted at University of North Carolina HC System Chapel Hill, NC	Assessment of: Extent the organization is a "learning organ." Level of nurse involvement in LEAN improvement at unit level Patient-centered focus of the organ. Visual management and feedback	Instrument is helpful in measuring level of LEAN penetration in organ. LEAN terminology and jargon is problematic Test fatigue—20 min to complete	Could be of value in DNP project in terms of the visual management component Perhaps useful tool to demonstrate staff involvement in improvement activities
Examine if hosp with better work environ have better value (Silber et al., 2016)	Retrospective matched-cohort Compare outcomes and costs of pts at 35 hosp known for positive nursing wrk environ vs. 293 control group	25,752 elderly Medicare gen surg pts at focal hosp 62,882 pts at control hosp	30-day mortality Costs=resource utilization	Positive nurse work environ hospitals vs. controls: 30-day mortality = 4.8 vs. 5.8 Cost/pt = \$163 less	Hospitals with better work environ for nurses have better outcomes and better value in terms of cost

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
		Hosp in Illinois, NY and Tx in 2015		= better value Cost effectiveness best with patients at higher risk	Useful in demonstrating importance of Pos work environment that can be achieved through engagement in perf improvement activities
Relationship between nursing teamwork and NDNQI outcomes (Rahn, 2016)	Descriptive Nonprobability convenience sample Reading, PA	8 units of 735 bed hospital Acute care med/surg RNs, UAP 154 Surveys returned	IV= Nursing teamwork DV=NDNQI data on falls, pressure ulcers, CAUTI	Most teams lack long-term member stability Overall orientation of the team provides highest challenge=what is in best interest of team vs. individual Best functioning teams had lower incidence of falls and CAUTIs	Weak association between teamwork and NDNQI indicators. Authors say more study needed Not that helpful

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Linkages between nursing and quality of care (Naylor et al., 2013)	Meta-analysis Following INQRI	389 studies identified (2005- 2009) 161 studies included in quantitative synthesis		Result findings organized in around: Aims, designs interventions, outcomes, study findings & conclusions Majority of non- experimental studies found + association between nursing and quality Quasi-experimental found increase in number of studies but decrease in studies demonstrating + association Experimental studies typically ident + association between nursing and quality	Great sources of studies showing relationship of nursing to quality of care

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Staff Feedback					
Assess if Feedback intervention Theory from org psychology explains obs variability in HC A&F research (Hysong, 2009)	Meta-Analysis Hedges-Olkin method for meta anal Feedback content Feedback format Feedback Longitudinal qualitative Semi-structured interviews frequency	Studies cited in prior 06(Ivers et al., 2006) systematic review & newer studies 19 10 Members of staff receiving intervention Newcastle upon Tyne, UK studies incl.	Correct solution info Written feedback Verbal feedback Graphic feedback	Frequent, individual, non-punitive feedback effective helps in adherence with cl guidelines. Indust/organ psych FIT positively associated with HC feedback Feedback that included indication of correct solution most effective	A&F is effective in changing provider behavior and quality care Reports with suggestions for improvement most effective Written reports most effective when delivered frequently Limits; Large number of studies excluded from 519 only 19 incl Good Meta for showing importance of feedback.

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Effects of clinical feedback to surg residents (Lau et al., 2016)	Prospective cohort Effective prescription of VTE prophylaxis in surg patients. Two interventions: 1. Implementation of scorecard for surg residents 2. Implementation of scorecard + individual counseling	49 Gen Surg residents Johns Hopkins Hosp. Baltimore, MD	Baseline data collected # of pts receiving appropriate VTE prophylaxis # of residents that were 100% accurate in prescribing VTE prophylaxis before interventions and after.	Baseline 89.4% pts. prescribed appropriate VTE prophylaxis & 45% of resident phys prescribed approp VTE for <u>every</u> pt. When scorecard only impl, ↑95.4 pts. received approp VTE Prophylaxis & 61% of resident phys prescribed approp VTE for <u>every</u> pt. Scorecard + counseling= 96.4 pts received approp VTE prophylaxis & 78% of resident phys prescribed approp VTE for <u>every</u> pt.	Feedback using a scorecard where data related to actual performance is provided increases performance. Scorecard + individual counseling even more effective Useful in looking at feedback regarding performance on NSIs at unit level.

Purpose; Author/Date	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Dashboards & Other Feedback Strategies					
Identify key barriers and inhibitors to using nursing unit-specific dashboards (Jeffs et al., 2014)	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews	500-bed acute care hospital 56 nurses interviewed: 51 front-line nurses 5 nurse managers Toronto, Canada	Interviews verbatim transcript 5 study leaders independently evaluated and categories comments into themes	Nurse leaders play a key role in supporting staff to engage in PI Leaders need to create supportive learning environ. Educators, QI nurses, informal unit leaders all must collaborate Need to identify champions for data feedback using dashboards Busy work environ. are key barriers to use of dashboards Need to have ongoing unit-based discussions as to what data men and	Data needs to be displayed in many ways: white boards, computer screens, hard copy on bulletin boards Must create the milieu where PI is valued Unit leaders need to educate staff re; dashboard, conduct staff meeting to assess data and develop corrective approaches Good study to document perceptions of dashboards by

Purpose;	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results / Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Author/Date				relationship to care outcomes	staff and potential barriers

Note. AECOPD = Acute Exacerbations of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease; A&F = Audit and Feedback; CAUTI = Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection; CAP = Community-Acquired Pneumonia; FIT = Feedback Intervention Theory; NDNQI = National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators; SDS = Sociodemographic status; SR = Systems Redesign; INQNRI = International Nursing Quality Research Initiative; UAP = Unlicensed Assistive Personnel